

TENSES

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Abstract: The following article examines the types of verb tenses in Uzbek and English and explains their differences and uses. The main content of the article will help students learning English as a second foreign language to fully understand the meaning of verb ratios in both languages.

Key words: verb, tense, affix, inflection, past tense, category.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о глаголе и его категории времени и формах прошедшего времени глагола. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются формы форм прошедшего времени в староузбекском языке и в нашем современном узбекском языке.

Ключевые слова: глагол, время, аффикс, словоизменение, прошедшее время, категория.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu magolada fe'l va uning zamon kategoriyasi hamda o 'tgan zamon fe'? shakilari hagida so'z boradi. Bundan tashgari magolada eski o'zbektilida va hozigi o'zbek tilimizdao tgan zamon shakllari ganday shakida bo 'Iganligi xususida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: fe'l, zamon, affiks, tushlash, o 'tgan zamon, kategoriya.

Speaking about the grammatical nature of verb, it should be emphasized that the verb is one of the main word groups and differs from other word groups by its meaning, grammatical forms and syntactic functions. A verb relates an action, existence, state, and relationship to a verb in the form of a process, with a time perspective. A verb is a group of words that expresses an action, state or process

and has such grammatical categories as tense, aspect, inclination, proportion, perfect, modality and so on. Verbs are words that mean action. Verbs express the action of a certain subject in a sentence. A verb is a group of words rich in complex categories. Grammatical categories of verbs are expressed by contrasting synthetic or analytical forms of words belonging to the group of verbs. The category of grammatical tense is the most common in languages, is one of the common verb categories.

*Ochil buvaning gapi menga ham ta'sir **qildi**, azizlarim. [1;142]*

I worked at the hospital last year. [3; 20]

We use the **Past simple** to express an action that happened in the past. Focus on the verbs for the sentence in this tense. That is, after the possessor (I, he, she, it, we, you, they), the suffix **ed** is added to the verb (if it is a correct verb). If there is an **irregular verb**, we mark the irregular verb itself as special. That is, the picture in line 2 (from the table of incorrect verbs).

*O'qishlar boshlanib o'quvchilar maktabga **kelyapti**. [4; 258]*

*He **knows** that I am here, and I am in this dreadful condition. [5;154]*

It changes depending on the inflection of the present simple tense. In the third person singular (**he, she, it**), the letter **-s** is added to the main verb in demonstrative sentences. If the verb ends with the letters **-o, -ch, -sh, -ss, -s, -x**, the verb The letters **-es** must be added. If it ends with the letter **-y**, the letter **-y** changes to the letter **-i** and then **-es** is added.

*Hech kimga bildirmay ikki kunda kelinni **keltirdilar**. [1; 39]*

I will go to the store tomorrow [6; 51]

Future tense is an adverb for simple future action-energy. Future tense adverbs take part in the sentence. In the sentence, the verb **will** is placed after the possessor and the main verb is for the **infinitive**.

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